

FileName	LineNumber	ACCOUNTNUMBER	CHNAME	CHSOCIAL	ADDRESS1	ADDRESS2
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26309	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26310	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26311	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26312	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26313	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26314	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26315	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26316	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26317	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26318	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26319	[Redacted]	WYNTER,BARON	[Redacted]	6720 BUCKINGHAM PL	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26320	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26321	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26322	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26323	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26324	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26325	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26326	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26327	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26328	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_092022	26329	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

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